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Implementing Active Learning Strategies to Improve EFL Learners' Reading Skills

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the Master's Degree in Applied Linguistics

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Abstract

This study was conducted on 40 intermediate-level learners of English as a foreign language at the Higher Language Institute at Damascus University in Damascus, Syria. The 40 learners were evenly distributed into two groups: an experimental group and a control group. The main purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of teaching reading skills through active learning techniques such as jigsaw and think-pair-share. It also aims at determining whether applying active learning techniques can enhance the level of classroom participation. Moreover, the current study attempts to gauge the attitudes of learners towards the utilized active learning techniques. Quantitative and qualitative data were gathered by employing a questionnaire, pre- and posttest and classroom participation rubric. The experimental group was instructed using the active learning techniques, whereas the control group was instructed in a traditional way over the span of two weeks. The findings of this study indicate that the implemented active learning techniques had a positive impact on learners' performance and engagement. Learners were motivated to learn with each other and enjoyed sharing their experiences and views during the learning process. The results also showed that learners' reading skills were improved significantly. Thus, it is recommended integrating active learning techniques in the EFL reading classes.

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List of Abbreviations

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

ESL: English as a Second Language

GTM: Grammar Translation Method

HLL: Higher Language Institute

HOTS: Higher-order thinking skills

LOTS: Lower-order thinking skills

P-value: Probability Value

PBL: Problem-Based Learning

SPSS: Statistical Package for Social Science

TAPPS: Think Aloud Pair Problem Solving

TPS: Think-Pair-Share

ZPD: Zone of Proximal Development

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Active learning is an instructional approach that shifts the attention from the teacher to the student. In such an approach, the teacher's role has changed from being "the sage on the stage" to a "guide on the side" (King, 1998, p. 30). Active learning can take several forms all of which aim to provide students with opportunities to get involved in the learning process and require them to take ownership of their own learning. Learners are no longer perceived as empty vessels to be filled with knowledge by the teacher. The teacher's main responsibility is to make sure that learners take on an active role in the learning process (Bonwell & Eison, 1991; King, 1998). This approach to learning has been used to teach different language skills including reading.

Reading is an essential language skill. Since EFL learners have rare opportunities to speak with native speakers, reading seems to be the most significant language skill especially in the academic contexts (Rivers, 1981; Grabe, 1991). It is also viewed as a means of communication between the reader and the writer and a window that overlooks on the target language culture. Moreover, reading allows individuals to "access knowledge, expand their views of the world, and develop their critical-thinking skills" (Ferrer & Staley, 2016, p. 79). In other words, it does not only serve as a source of information, but it is also a means to extend the reader's knowledge. It also exposes the reader to a wide range of vocabulary in context and new grammatical structures.

Research into second and foreign language reading has increased in recent decades (Grabe, 1991). Reading is no longer regarded as a passive activity. Instead, it is considered an active process in which readers build meaning by linking their background knowledge with the information presented in the text (Nunan, 2003). Therefore, readers are not regarded as passive

decoders of letters and words but rather creators of meaning. To create knowledge and meaning out of printed pages, students are required to deploy various skills such as activating their background knowledge, scanning, skimming, inferencing, and predicting. Thus, when it comes to EFL reading instruction, the teacher should take on the role of a facilitator and mentor to help students “construct meaning as they apply their current knowledge to new ideas” (Teo et al., 2016, p. 20). Reading lessons should be carefully planned and delivered through various interactive activities.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Based on the researcher’s experience, much class time is spent on spoon-feeding students with information. Students are assigned a passive role, whereas the teacher dominates the class most of the time. Such an approach is known as teacher-centered. This approach to teaching minimizes the students’ role to mere passive listeners, recipients of information and note takers. Teacher-centered approach is considered to have little effect on students’ learning growth (Duckworth, 2009).

The teacher-centered approach is often utilized in EFL reading classes (Berenji, 2021; Khoja & Mohapatra, 2017). In some Syrian educational settings, teachers translate the reading text word by word and give students lists of unfamiliar vocabulary to be learned and memorized by heart, which is similar to what happens in the Grammar-Translation Method (GTM) (Khoja & Mohapatra, 2017). Thus, there is a need to incorporate a student-centered approach where students learn by themselves and the teachers’ main job is to plan and organize the learning activities.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

This study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. Investigate the effects of implementing active learning techniques on intermediate-level learners’ reading ability.

2. Promote learners' participation level in the classroom.
3. Discover learners' attitudes towards active learning techniques.

1.4 Research Questions

There are three key questions to the present study:

1. What is the effect of using active learning techniques on improving EFL learners' reading skills?
2. To what extent learners' participation level will be improved?
3. What are the students' perceptions of using active learning techniques in teaching reading skills?

1.5 Significance of the Research

The significance of the current study emerges from the fact that it attempts to determine the effectiveness of using an active learning approach to teach various reading skills. This study is also significant for teachers at the HLI as it provides them with a set of alternative techniques to deliver EFL intermediate learners the reading lessons effectively and motivate them to enhance their reading skills. These techniques are likely to foster students' participation in the classroom. In addition, it provides EFL curriculum designers with various activities that contribute to the development of future English curricula and hence can be implemented while teaching reading. It attempts to engage students in the learning process by giving them an active role in the process of creating meaning and relating the learning materials to their personal experiences.

1.6 Operational Terms Definition

The most cited and widely acceptable definition of **active learning** is the one Bonwell and Eison proposed. They defined active learning as "involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing" (Bonwell & Eison, 1991, p. 1). In fact, active learning is a broad term that includes various methods that all have in common the aim of engaging students

in the learning process such as cooperative learning, collaborative learning, problem-based learning and many others.

Generally speaking, **English as a Foreign Language (EFL)** refers to studying English in a country or location where English is not used as a means of communication. In contrast, **English as a Second Language (ESL)** denotes studying English in a country where English is “the main language of communication for most people.” (Oxford, 2017, p. 341)

Jigsaw is a cooperative learning technique where students are required to work in groups to achieve a common goal (Prince, 2004). This technique is regarded as an efficient way to learn new information as it allows learners to take on crucial role in the learning process. Learners are expected to listen to each other and show engagement in the materials in hand.

Learner’s schema (schemata) refers to the background knowledge that the learner has about a given topic or text and its functions (Ausubel, 1963). The theory of schema, which is originated from constructivism, asserts that people develop schemata for “everything they know, including people, places, things, processes and skills” (Tracey & Morrow, 2017, p. 60). Thus, text comprehension can rely on schemata which help learners understand new facts, text types, formal patterns and practices (Hedgcock & Ferris, 2018).

Think-pair-share (TPS) is a collaborative learning technique developed by Lyman in 1981 where students pair up and figure out an answer to a question or a solution to a problem. This technique allows interaction and requires accountability. It also fosters students’ engagement and motivates them to think first, then share their thoughts with their peers and gain further knowledge from them (Robertson, 2006).

Concept mapping: is a way of representing and organizing new concepts and highlighting the relationship between them (Novak & Canas, 2007). Learners are expected to grasp the material by transferring “the written content into concrete images” (Liu, Chen, & Chang, 2010, p. 442).

Reading skills: Leipzig (2002) as cited in (Sapsuha & Bugis, 2013) identifies word recognition and comprehension to be essential components of reading. As comprehension is regarded as the ultimate goal of any reading activity, vocabulary knowledge can assist readers to achieve this goal (Carroll, 1993).

1.7 Organization of the Study

This dissertation is divided into five chapters followed by references and appendices. The first chapter consists of a brief background of the research, the problem that the research addresses, aims of the study, research questions, and the significance of the study. It also highlighted some key operational terms. In chapter two, the theoretical background of active learning and reading skill is reviewed in depth. In addition, previous studies, which were conducted in relation to the present study are highlighted. Chapter three deals with the methodology used in the current study, including the context of the study, data collection instruments and research procedures. The findings of this study are discussed in chapter four. The last chapter of this piece of work highlights the limitations and recommendations for further research.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2.0. Introduction

This chapter explores the literature relevant to this study. It is divided into three main parts. While the first part, the theoretical framework, sheds light on important aspects related to the concept of active learning, the second part discusses key features that have to do with reading skills. The third part is divided into two sections. The first section deals with previous studies that were carried out in different contexts. The second section considers the difference between the previous studies and the current study.

2.1. Active Learning: An Overview

In this section, the definition of active learning as well as its theoretical background are presented. A comparison between the active learning and traditional learning is also drawn. In addition, some benefits and certain types of active learning are highlighted. Vital constructs of active learning such as learner's participation and engagement are also discussed.

2.1.1. Active Learning Definition

Faust & Paulson (1998, p. 4) argue that active learning refers to “any learning activity engaged in by students in the classroom other than listening passively to an instructor’s lecture.” Similarly, Prince (2004, p. 1) defines active learning as “any instructional method that engages students in the learning process and requires students to do meaningful learning and thinking about what they are doing.” He further adds that the core elements of active learning are “student activity and engagement” in the learning process. Carr, Palmer and Hagel (2015, p. 174) recognize the cognitive aspect of active learning suggesting that active learning refers to “students’ efforts to actively construct their knowledge.” Allen and Tanner (2005, p. 262) describe active learning as a form of “looking for new information, organizing this information in a meaningful way, and getting the chance to explain it to others.” Lumpkin,

Achen and Dodd (2015, p. 123) consider active learning a form of “activity encouraging students to participate in learning approaches, engaging them with course material and enhancing critical thinking as they make applications beyond the classroom.”

2.1.2 Active Learning in a Constructivist Framework

The term “active learning” is based on the theory of constructivism. In fact, it is a hybrid of both cognitive and social constructivism. According to the cognitive constructivist theory of learning, knowledge is a state of understanding that only exists in the mind of the individual learner. Piaget (1976, p. 116) asserts that “children do not receive knowledge passively but rather discover and construct knowledge through activities.” In a similar way, students regardless of their age need to engage in activities with teachers, peers and presented materials to form their own mental structures (Meyers & Jones, 1993). In order for learning to take place, Ausubel (1963) suggests that learners need to accommodate the new information into their existing knowledge. To do so, he identifies three main cognitive processes that learners need to activate. These processes involve (1) selecting relevant information, (2) organizing the new information in a meaningful way and (3) connecting this information to their prior knowledge. Mayer (1998) agrees with Ausubel and adds that active learning techniques require learners to activate these processes. He states

Instructional methods aimed at active learning seek to engage the learner’s cognitive processes such as helping the learner select relevant information, organize that information into coherent representation, and integrate that representation with existing knowledge. (p.368)

Additionally, social constructivists assert that students construct their knowledge when they interact with each other and with the environment where they live. Dewey (1938) considers learning as a social practice with students interacting with their professor and other students while engaging with the material. Furthermore, Vygotsky (1978) establishes the concept of Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which suggests that learning takes place when learners solve problems beyond their current developmental level with the help of their instructor or

their peers. In other words, learners bridge the gap between what they already know and what to be learnt with the assistance of an advanced peer or teacher.

Watkins, Carnell and Lodge (2007, p. 71) recognize the behavioral aspect of active learning. They affirm that active learning engages learners' energies among three parts: behavioral, cognitive and social. The behavioral part means "actively using and creating materials", while the cognitive part refers to "actively thinking [and] constructing new meaning." The social part, however, means to "actively [get] engag[ed] with others [such] as collaborators and resources." Thus, active learning can be regarded as a social and cognitive approach where learners interact with and help each other understand new materials and form their knowledge about a given topic.

2.1.3. Active Learning versus Traditional Learning

To understand the concept and features of active learning, it is better to draw a contrast between the traditional classroom and the active one. Johnson, Johnson and Smith (1998) made such a distinction and affirmed that the traditional or transmittal approach is teacher-centered. The teacher transmits knowledge to students by pouring that knowledge into their empty receptacles. Learners are passive listeners whose main role is to memorize transmitted knowledge. They are encouraged to compete with each other instead of cooperating and working with one another. Additionally, it is assumed that any person with good expertise can teach without the need for training.

On the contrary, active learning is a learner-centered approach. The emphasis is placed on student's cooperation rather than competition. The teacher facilitates the learning process and students' interaction with the material and each other. Students become active constructors of knowledge as most class time is allotted to participating and reflecting on learning. The teacher provides learners with opportunities to take responsibility for their own learning. In addition, teachers need to be trained on how to integrate such activities in the learning process. Table 2.1 presents a summary of each approach of teaching.

Table 2.1 *A Comparison of Old & New Paradigms of Teaching*

Factor	Old Paradigm of Teaching	New Paradigm of Teaching
Knowledge	Transferred from faculty to students	Jointly constructed by students and faculty
Students	Passive vessel to be filled by faculty's knowledge	Active constructors, discoverers, transformers of knowledge.
Nature of learning	Learning is fundamentally individual; requires extrinsic motivation	Learning is fundamentally social; requires supportive environment / community to unleash intrinsic motivation.
Faculty Purpose	Classify and sort students	Develop students' competencies and talents
Relationships	Impersonal relationships among students and between faculty and students.	Personal transaction among students and between faculty and students.
Context	Competitive/ individualistic	Cooperative learning in classroom and cooperative teams among faculty.
Assumption	Any expert can teach	Teaching is complex and requires considerable training.

Note: A comparison of old & new paradigms of teaching. Adapted from "Active learning: cooperation in the college classroom" by Johnson, Johnson and Smith (1998).

2.1.4 Active Learning Benefits

There are a number of benefits that can be gained from implementing active learning techniques in the classroom. Komarraju and Karau (2008) emphasize that active learning increases learning. It is also suggested by King (1998, p. 35) that active learning always leads to "deeper understanding" and helps learners become "knowledge producers, critical

thinkers and creative problem solvers.” Nilson (1998, p.150) as cited in (Cherney, 2011) explains that any student-active method ensures “higher student motivation, more learning at higher cognitive levels, and longer retention of information.” Prince (2004) and Cherney (2008) also affirm that information presented through active learning is better recalled. Cavanagh (2011) agrees with them and adds that active learning leads to better student attitudes and more self-directed learning. Freeman et al. (2014) conclude in their research that active learning improves students’ performance and engagement. Similarly, McCarthy and Anderson (2000) affirm that active learning techniques increase class participation and lead to higher motivation as well. Figure 2.1 represents the percentage of information retained through the use of active learning in comparison with passive learning.

Figure 2.1 *The Effect of Active Learning on Student’s Retention*

Note: Effect of Active Learning on Student’s Retention. Adapted from “Active learning: Using Bloom’s taxonomy to support critical pedagogy,” by Tabrizi, S., & Rideout, G. (2017) *IJCDSE*, 8(3), 3202, 3209.

2.1.5 Active Learning and Bloom's Taxonomy

Active learning tasks require students to get engaged in higher-order thinking activities rather than passively receiving information (King, 1998; Freeman, et al., 2014; Fobes & Kaufman, 2008). Machemer and Crawford (2007, p. 10) emphasize that active learning provides students with opportunities “to reflect, evaluate, analyze, synthesize and communicate on the information presented.” The effectiveness of any teaching methods is often determined by utilizing the revised Bloom's taxonomy of the cognitive skills. Bloom's taxonomy consists of six levels which are divided into Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) and Lower-Order Thinking Skills (LOTS). While the HOTS include analyzing, evaluating and creating, the LOTS contain remembering, understanding and applying. In teacher-centered environments, learners tend to learn facts rather than deep concepts. Thus, learning in a teacher-controlled classroom does not exceed the lower levels of Bloom's taxonomy. On the contrary, in an active learning or a student-centered environment, learners are given the chance to create, evaluate and analyze the materials they deal with by interacting with each other. Figure 2.2 represents the revised version of Bloom's taxonomy.

Figure 2.2 *The Revised Bloom's Taxonomy*

Note: The Revised Bloom's Taxonomy. Adapted from "A taxonomy for learning, teaching and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy" by Anderson, L.W. et al., (1992), New York, Longman Publishing

2.1.6 Active Learning Methods

Active learning refers to several student-centered methods such as cooperative, collaborative and problem-based learning (Prince, 2004, Chatmon, Chi, Davis, 2010, Bonwell & Esion, 1991). Each of these methods has a set of techniques that can be performed in the EFL classroom.

2.1.6.1 Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning is viewed as an umbrella term that encompasses all group-based instructional methods including cooperative learning. Much like cooperative learning, collaborative learning requires students to work together in small groups to achieve a common goal. It also highlights the importance of learners' interaction rather than learning as a solitary activity (Prince, 2004).

2.1.6.2 Cooperative Learning

Cooperative learning is considered as the most commonly used form of active learning (Tsay & Brady, 2010). It is a structured form of group work where students to work in small groups with one another to achieve a common goal. Students' knowledge is assessed individually often by taking a short quiz. Much emphasis is placed on cooperation rather than competitive or individualistic learning. Cooperative learning establishes five elements: positive interdependence, individual accountability, face-to-face promotive interaction, interpersonal and small group skills and group processing (Veenman, Kenter, & Post, 2000; Prince, 2004; Johnson, Johnson, & Smith, 1998). Positive interdependence, which is regarded as the core element of cooperative learning, emphasizes that student's success depends on the success of all groupmates. Individual accountability refers to evaluating students' performance individually and reporting back the results to the group members and the individual learner. Face-to-face interaction refers to group members' efforts to explain, discuss and teach each other what they know. Interpersonal and small group skills stress that group members need to use social and collaborative skills in order to function effectively. These skills involve decision-making, trust-building, communication and conflict management skills. Finally, group processing refers to a process of evaluating that group members should continuously perform in order to achieve the expected goals (Johnson, Johnson, & Smith, 1998).

2.1.6.3 Problem-Based Learning (PBL)

Similarly, the problem-based learning method refers to an instructional method where students cooperate with one another to solve a relevant problem introduced at the beginning of the class. This method requires students to be self-directed and assume an active role. Students need to explore the issue, identify the problem and list down possible solutions. Learning becomes active as they discover the content that is essential for solving

the problem (Prince, 2004; Zayapragassarazan & Kumar, 2012; Chatmon, Chi, & Davis, 2010).

All in all, the aforementioned methods hold in common student cooperation and engagement in the learning process to construct knowledge. Other active learning methods may include team-based learning and flipped classrooms, which are not of an interest in the present study.

2.1.7 Active Learning Techniques

Since active learning is an encompassing term that includes other methods of learning such as cooperative learning, collaborative learning and problem-based learning, it has a wide range of techniques that all share the aim of engaging students in the learning process (Prince, 2004; Faust & Paulson, 1998; Anthony, 1996; Chatmon, Chi, & Davis, 2010).

Jigsaw, which is one of the techniques implemented in this study, is a cooperative learning technique where the teacher arranges the context and facilitates the learning process. The teacher divides the materials into no more than five or six parts. Students are assigned to groups known as “home groups” with as many members as there are parts to the learning materials, and each group member receives one part of the materials. Students with the same part of the materials form new groups known as “expert groups”, where they discuss the materials to be learnt. After that, students return to their home groups and each student explains to their group members their part. Finally, students are tested individually to assess their understanding of the complete set of material (Aronson et al. 1978, cited in King, 1998).

Another technique that is used in the current study is think-pair-share. It is a collaborative learning technique in which students work together to solve a problem or answer a question about an assigned reading task. As the name suggests, this technique

consists of three stages. In the first stage (think), the teacher poses a question that usually needs evaluating and asks students to think about a possible answer for some time. In the second stage (pair), the teacher asks students to share their responses with partners. During the final stage (share), students are asked to share their responses with the entire group or class (Millis, 2012).

Concept mapping is a way of representing knowledge graphically. The origin of this technique is based on David Ausubel's theory of assimilation (1963), which suggests that meaningful learning occurs when learners relate new information to relevant information that already exists in the learners' cognitive system. Creating such maps requires selecting relevant concepts, arranging them hierarchically, and determining the relationships between them. In fact, concept mapping helps students see how several concepts are related to each other (Faust & Paulson, 1998) and reinforces knowledge retention (Teo et al., 2016). Additionally, using concept mapping as a while and post-reading technique can help readers organize their knowledge in a systematic way and increase their interest in learning about the topic (Trang, 2017).

Other active learning techniques may also include one-minute paper, clearest/muddiest idea, value line, clarification pauses, peer-review, panel discussions, debates, quizzes, fishbowl, three-step interview, Thinking-Aloud Pair Problem Solving (TAPPS), send/pass a problem, constructive controversy, games, daily/weekly journal, flash cards, role play, mind maps and co-op co-op (Faust & Paulson, 1998; King, 1998; Millis, 2012).

2.1.8 Learner's Participation

One important aspect of active learning is that it aims at enhancing learners' participation in the classroom. Heyman and Sailors (2011, p. 605) describe classroom participation as "a form of active learning in which students publicly discuss the course

materials.” In addition, Crosthwaite, Bailey and Meeker (2015, p. 2) define classroom participation as “playing an active role in all in-class activities.” Vandricks (2000) suggests that participation requires students to speak in class by asking and answering questions, making comments and participating in discussions. The aforesaid definitions donate that learners should be encouraged to speak, take on a central role in the class and contribute effectively and meaningfully in the class.

According to Petress (2006, p. 1) participation has three dimensions. These dimensions involve “quantity, dependability and quality.” While the quantity dimension refers to the opportunities that students have to express their ideas and opinions, the quality dimension is the regular interaction in class in which students demonstrate their awareness of the topic of discussion. Dependability, however, means the ability to rely on students to make relevant and constructive contributions. Therefore, student’s participation should be recurrent, meaningful and related to the task in hand.

Learners’ participation can have various benefits. Weaver (2005, p. 570) claims that “students who participate in the learning process learn more than those who do not”. In addition, students who participate actively have the opportunity to practice their target language, and improve their critical reading and understanding of the materials (Sánchez-Hernández, Vez-López, & García-Barrios, 2021). When students are encouraged to participate in classroom activities, they take responsibility for their learning (Mohd, Noor, & Maizatul, 2012) as cited in (Sánchez-Hernández, Vez-López, & García-Barrios, 2021).

2.1.9 Student Engagement

One of the primary goals of active learning is to increase student engagement in class (Odum, Meaney, & Knudson, 2021). Bachman and Bachman (2011), argue that higher level of engagement leads to better learning. Fredricks, Blumenfeld and Pairs (2004) recognize three types of engagement: (1) behavioral, (2) emotional and (3) cognitive.

Behavioral engagement refers to getting involved in learning tasks through exerting effort, displaying concentration and attention, and contributing to class discussion. Emotional engagement entails students' affective reactions in the classroom such as interest, boredom or anxiety. Cognitive engagement is concerned with incorporating the learner's willingness and thoughtfulness to exert the necessary effort to understand complex ideas and master difficult skills.

Chi and Wylie (2014) propose a framework for student engagement based on overt behaviors that learners need to display during the learning process. This framework, known as ICAP hypothesis, involves four modes of behaviors: interactive, constructive, active and passive. Each of these engagement behaviors represents a level of learning. Not only does this framework is useful for clarifying the engagement behaviors but it also predicts the possible cognitive outcomes for each mode.

The first mode of engagement behaviors is the passive mode which is represented by the last letter of the acronym "P". The reason why Chin and Wylie begin with the last phase is that they aim to establish that interactive engagement is the ultimate goal of teachers. This mode involves listening and receiving information from the instructor and the instructional materials. Learners do not engage in any visible activity related to the learning tasks.

The second mode of engagement "A" is the active mode. This level emphasizes that learners need to perform activities that show manipulation of the learning materials. Unlike the passive mode, learners show focused attention while manipulating the learning materials. In this mode, learners are engaged in activities such as underlining or highlighting texts, summarizing, pausing or rewinding videos.

The third mode of engagement is the constructive mode 'C', which subsumes active and constructive modes. In this mode, learners generate and infer new ideas that are not

included in the presented materials. In doing so, learners reflect on the provided materials from a personal perspective. In other words, when the student repeats the materials in an activity or uses the same provided instruction without creating or adding new personalized thoughts or ideas, then she or he exhibits an active action rather than a constructive one. Learners can make concept maps, take notes in one's words, draw analogies and make comparisons and contrasts.

The interactive mode of engagement 'I' is the final and highest mode of engagement which combines both the constructive mode and the active mode. This mode requires one or three learners to undertake activities that enable them to reflect on the learning materials. Learners' interaction should be constructive, in that learners' contributions should be new, unique and beyond what is explicitly given in the information presented. Table 2.2 summarizes the main points of each type of engagement.

Table 2.2 *ICAP Hypothesis*

Category	Passive	Active	Constructive	Interactive
Hypothesis	P>	A>	C>	I>
Characteristic	Receiving	Manipulating	Generating	Dialoguing
Definition	Merely paying attention to receive the learning material	Manipulating learning materials to focus attention	Generating new inferences or information beyond what is presented	Generating additional inferences and information via dialoguing with a peer

Knowledge-Change Processes	Co-Infering (taking turns, mutual benefit)	Infering connecting, comparing, reflecting		Storing Isolated, encapsulated information
Cognitive Outcomes	Recalling knowledge in identical contexts.	Applying knowledge to similar contexts.	Transferring knowledge to new or distant contexts.	Co-creating or inventing new ideas and products.
Learning Outcomes	Minimal understanding	Shallow understanding	Deep understanding	Deepest understanding
Learning activities	-Listen to a lecture -Read an article -Watch a video	-Take notes -Highlight key information -Pause or replay	-Reflect out loud -Summarize in new words -Compare to another video	-Defend a position in a group -Ask and answer in pairs -Debate justification with a peer

Note: ICAP Hypothesis. Adopted from “The ICAP framework: Linking cognitive engagement to active learning outcomes” by Chi, M.T & Wylie, R. 2014. *Educational Psychologist*, 49(4), 219-243.

2.2. Reading

This part of the chapter tackles the theoretical background of reading and presents different kinds of reading skills and models.

2.2.1 Reading Definition

Literature on reading shows different views on how to define reading skills. Grabe and Stoller (2011) define reading as the ability to draw meaning and understanding from written

text. Nunan (1999, p. 253) argues that reading is a process of “reconstructing meaning rather than decoding form.” Bojovic (2010, p. 1) views reading as an “interactive activity” in which readers employ their schemata as well as information from the written text. Nuttall (1996, p.4) concludes that the purpose of any reading activity is to “get a message from written texts.”

2.2.2. Reading as a Social and Cognitive Activity

Constructivism views reading as a process of communication between readers and the writers (Zahawi & Hasan, 2019). In fact, constructivists consider reading as a social practice in which readers are affected by their social context in terms of the way they read and the background knowledge they have on the topic that influences their understanding of written texts (Yang & Wilson, 2006).

Urquhart and Weir (1998) assert that reading is regarded as a cognitive activity that takes place in the mind. Readers are required to integrate their schemata and the new information from the text in producing meaning. Alderson (2000) recognizes an aspect of reading that calls for the use of problem-solving strategies to help figure out the meaning of unfamiliar words, for example.

In this study, reading is considered as a social and cognitive activity. Learners use different cognitive processes to acquire reading skills through collaborative and cooperative methods and interact with their classmates.

2.2.3 Reading Skills

Literature indicates an overlap between the term “skill” and “strategy”. While Nuttall (1996) uses the two terms interchangeably, many other educators make an effort to distinguish between them. Stoller and Grabe (2011, p. 8), define the term “skill” as “the linguistic processing abilities that are actively automatic in their use and combinations.” The term “Strategy”, however, refers to a “set of abilities under conscious control of the reader” (Grabe & Stoller, 2011, p. 8). Oxford (2017, p. 272), suggests that these strategies are “teachable,

dynamic thoughts and behaviors that learners consciously select and employ in specific contexts.” Williams and Moran (1989) also draw a distinction between reading strategies and skills. Reading strategies are reader-oriented which readers use unconsciously to solve a problem. Reading skills, however, are text-oriented that readers use subconsciously. Nevertheless, in the realm of EFL reading, the term “skill” can substitute “strategy” (Tomlinson and Ellis, 1988, Walter, 1982, Barr et al., 1981, cited in Williams and Moran, 1989).

Reading includes a wide range of sub-skills that readers can make use of to achieve a better understanding of written texts. Grabe (1991, p. 379) identifies six skills that readers need to possess. First, learners need to have automatic recognition skills such as decoding. Moreover, vocabulary and structural knowledge is a crucial skill for learners. This includes the ability to recognize new vocabulary and different types of sentence structures. Additionally, readers should have good knowledge of formal discourse structure such as knowing how a certain text is organized influences the comprehension of the text. Readers’ background knowledge and prior information related to the topic of the text can also have an impact on reading comprehension. Nonetheless, comprehension is not the only aim of fluent readers but rather they seek to evaluate and synthesize the text information and compare it with other sources of knowledge. Finally, Grabe argues that readers should possess metacognitive knowledge and monitoring skills. While the metacognitive knowledge involves scanning, skimming, previewing and guessing word meaning, monitoring skills include recognizing problems with information presented in the text.

Besides the sub-skills specified by Grabe, Davis (1968) identifies four main reading skills: (1) identifying word meanings, (2) drawing inferences, (3) identifying writer’s technique, (4) finding answers to questions. According to Munby (1978), reading skills include the ability to (1) recognize the language of the script, (2) deduce the meaning, (3) use of unfamiliar lexical items, (4) understand explicitly and indexicality stated information, (5) skimming, (6) scanning, (7) referencing (8) summarizing and (9) distinguishing main idea from supporting details.

2.2.4 Reading Models

Reading models refer to a range of processes that readers may adopt while approaching a text. This includes “skills, strategies, attentional resources, knowledge resources and their integration” (Grabe & Stoller, 2011). These models can be sequential, in which the reading process is viewed as “a series of stages each of which is complete before the next stage begins” (Urquhart & Weir, 1998, p. 39), or they can be simultaneous, which means multiple skills and processes should be activated at the same time (Hedgcock & Ferris, 2018). These models include the bottom-up, top-down and interactive models.

2.2.4.1 Bottom-up Models

The bottom-up model was first introduced by Gough in 1972. It is a grapheme-phoneme based approach which assumes that the reading process is initiated as the reader receives the textual input, recognizes letters and words, assigns sound to these words and works out words and sentence meaning. Simply put, reading is merely a decoding process that does not require the use of prior knowledge nor reflecting on the textual information. According to Urquhart and Weir (1998, p. 40), reading is regarded in this model as a “reading aloud process”. This model is regarded to be more appropriate for poor readers. According to Oxford (2017), the grammar translation method encourages the use of this model of reading regardless of how proficient the learners are. This model has been criticized for minimizing and restricting the reader’s role to a decoder of letters and ignoring other context cues (Williams and Moran, 1989).

2.2.4.2 Top-down Models

This model stands in sharp contrast to the bottom-up model. In fact, it is considered to be a constructivist-oriented approach which stresses the importance of the schemata that the reader brings to the text over the visual stimuli in the text (Alderson, 2000; Grabe & Stoller, 2011; Hedgcock & Ferris, 2018). The reader approaches the text with some expectations about the content. They confirm or disconfirm these expectations as they continue reading. To construct meaning from the text, Goodman (1982) identifies four procedures that the reader

deploys while reading. These procedures include sampling, predicting, confirming and correcting. Alderson (2000) explains these processes as follows:

Reading is a complex process of sampling the text for graphic clues, predicting grammatical structures and meaning, confirming the validity of the hypotheses and correcting the hypotheses as necessary as text sampling proceeds. (p.20)

However, this model does not take into consideration that the reader may have no assumptions about a given topic (Alderson, 2000). Similarly, in the case of EFL and ESL reading, the reader may have different assumptions about the topic due to cultural differences (Oxford, 2017).

2.2.4.3 Interactive Models

The interactive model, which was first proposed by Rumbelhart in 1977, is a combination of bottom-up and top-down models. According to this model, not only does the reader need a fast and efficient word recognition, but also they need to use their schemata to understand the text (Hedgcock & Ferris, 2018). Fast word recognition, schemata and predicting contribute to understanding the text (Alderson, 2000). Although Goodman (1982) is widely considered to be an advocate of the top-down model, he rejects this label. He argues that the process of constructing meaning requires readers to use the grapho-phonetic, syntactic and semantic cues interactively. Smith (1978) also asserts that readers should make use of visual and non-visual information while reading. By the visual information, Smith refers to the printed words on the page and contextual cues such as antonyms and synonyms, while the non-visual information refers to the background knowledge the reader already has.

This study makes use of the interactive model of reading since students are required to activate their background knowledge about a given topic and show decent decoding skills.

2.2.5 Active Reading Strategies

In order for active learning to occur, there are several strategies that learners can use while reading. First, learners can summarize the information presented in the text and make

inferences about it (Grabe & Stoller, 2011). Furthermore, the use of the metacognitive skills is vital during the process of reading. According to Baker and Brown (1980), learners should be able to monitor their comprehension as they read. Also, learners should possess the ability to self-correct their misunderstanding as they progress in their reading. Visualization is an important reading strategy as well as students use their mind capacity to imagine what the author's words are attempting to communicate to the reader. As a result, students create mental images that link new ideas to prior knowledge (Mills, 2009). Ultimately, the goal of using the aforementioned strategies is to obtain a greater understanding of the reading material. In other words, a deeper level of comprehension can be realized by activating these strategies.

2.2.6 Techniques of Reading

Intensive and extensive reading can be perceived as techniques to develop students' reading ability. Rivers (1981) differentiates between intensive and extensive reading. According to him, intensive reading aims to develop "greater control of the language in speech and writing under the teacher's guidance." The reading passage is meant to be studied in detail, concentrating on grammatical structures and vocabulary. On the other hand, the focus of extensive reading is on training students to read for enjoyment in the target language. In this technique of reading, students are required to read long reading texts such as those in newspapers or even entire novels. Skimming and scanning are also regarded as reading techniques used by students when teachers ask them to identify main ideas and look for specific information from reading passages (Hedgcock & Ferris, 2018).

2.3 Previous Studies

This section highlights different studies that were conducted in various contexts and implemented different active learning techniques to enhance class participation and teach reading skills.

2.3.1 Ragab (2018)

Ragab (2018) conducted quasi-experimental research to investigate the effect of implementing concept mapping technique on enhancing learners' reading skills. The study also aimed at examining learners' attitudes towards using this technique in reading classes. The participants of this study were 70 female secondary school students at an Egyptian public school. Learners were divided equally into a control group and experimental group. Learners of the control group were instructed using the traditional method, whereas learners of the experimental group were taught using the concept mapping technique. The treatment lasted for one semester. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected. The researcher used a pre- and posttest to evaluate learners' reading skills, and a questionnaire to measure their attitudes towards the concept mapping technique. The results showed that the scores of learners in the experimental group were better than those in the control group. Hence, learners' reading comprehension skill improved. The results also indicated that learners had a positive attitude towards using the concept mapping technique in reading classes.

2.3.2 Qadan (2018)

In her research, Qadan (2018) attempted to investigate the effect of using think-pair-share, jigsaw and five-fingers techniques on students' reading comprehension skills and their self-efficacy. Making inference, making prediction, making connection, skimming, discovering meaning were the main comprehension skills that were investigated. Participants were 72 fifth-grade male students evenly distributed into one control group and one experimental group. Data were collected through pre- and posttest to measure students' reading comprehension skills and a questionnaire to measure students' self-efficacy. The study was conducted during the first term at an elementary school in Gaza, Palestine. The study concluded that the implemented active learning techniques were effective in teaching reading comprehension skills. It also showed that the utilized active learning techniques could improve students' confidence in their ability to achieve the intended results.

2.3.3 Abrane (2019)

Abrane (2019) carried out an experimental study which aims to investigate the effect of using think-pair-share technique on developing EFL learners' vocabulary. Participants were 50 secondary school students. They were distributed equally into a control group and experimental group. The researcher taught learners in the experimental group through the use of TPS for four sessions. Each of these sessions was conducted within one hour. The topics that were covered during these sessions tackled confidence, stress, social media and personality. At the beginning of each class, learners were shown a video about a specific topic. Meanwhile, another teacher instructed learners in the control group using the traditional method. Data were gathered by the use of mainly a pre- and posttest. The pre- and posttest was comprised of four exercises: fill in the gaps, defining the word, matching the word with a synonym and matching the word with its definition. The results of the study suggest that utilizing TPS technique could improve learners' vocabulary retention.

2.3.4 Heswani (2019)

In her study, Heswani (2019) carried out this study to find out whether teaching English through the use of the flipped classroom can have an effect on learners' participation level. It also aimed at investigating learners' attitude towards the use of the flipped classroom during instruction. In this study, the researcher used the flipped classroom technique as a form of active learning. The researcher implemented several techniques to teach the content of the course, which the researcher herself designed. These techniques included think pair share, watching videos and group discussions. The researcher gathered qualitative and quantitative data through the use of a questionnaire, pre- and posttest, study log and participation rubric. Participants were 60 intermediate students divided into four groups. 30 students formed two experimental groups while the other 30 made up of two control groups. Students in the experimental groups received instruction through the flipped classroom technique, while students in the control groups were taught through the traditional instruction. The instruction was done over three

weeks. The results showed that learners had a positive attitude towards the use of the flipped classroom during instruction. It also demonstrated that learners' participation level significantly increased.

2.3.5 Tanapanyaworakul (2020)

Tanapanyaworakul (2020) employed experimental research to investigate the effectiveness of using the jigsaw technique on improving EFL learners' reading comprehension. This research also aimed at examining students' attitudes towards using this technique in reading instruction. Participants were nine-grade students at a Thai public school. The experiment was conducted on 16 students, while 50 students formed the control group. Learners of the experimental group were instructed using the jigsaw technique for five classes. The duration of each class was 90 minutes. The materials that were taught were extracted from websites that were suitable for A2-level students. The researcher collected both qualitative and quantitative data through the use of a pre- and posttest and questionnaire. The test was administered to measure students' reading performance, while the 15-item questionnaire was used to estimate learners' attitudes towards the jigsaw technique. The results of the study demonstrated learners' reading comprehension in the experimental group was better than that of learners in the control group. The results also indicated that learners had a positive attitude towards the use of jigsaw during reading class.

2.3.6 Namaziandost, Gilakjani and Hidayatullah (2020)

Namaziandost and his colleagues (2020) conducted this study to investigate the effect of using jigsaw technique on improving Iranian learners' EFL reading comprehension in a private institute. It was carried out on 50 pre-intermediate learners. 25 learners were instructed using the jigsaw technique (experimental group), while the other 25 learners were taught in the traditional method (control group). All participants were male aged between 16-18. The researchers administered a placement test to determine the English language proficiency level of the participants. Quantitative data were collected through pre-and posttest. The pre-and

posttest was made up of 40 multiple questions based on eight reading passages extracted from *Active Skills for Reading, Book 1* by Anderson (2008), and *Family and Friends 1* by Simmons (2009). The study showed that students who had received their instruction through the use of jigsaw outperformed those who had been taught through traditional instruction. It also concluded that the jigsaw technique could immerse learners in the learning process and helped them become independent learners.

2.3.7 Mundelsee & Jurkowski (2021)

Mundelsee and Jurkowski (2021) carried out this study which aims to investigate the effect of using TPS on in-class participation. To achieve this goal, the researchers used a pre- and post- questionnaire consisting of three dimensions, namely hand raising, shyness and state anxiety. The experiment was part of a communication training at a German secondary school. The training lasted a week and six trainers took part in this training. Participants were 481 nine graders from 16 different classes. The topics that were covered discussed wars, natural disasters, illnesses, education and poverty. The study reported that TPS had led to better classroom participation. Learners were more comfortable and confident about their answers.

2.3.8 Thongthee (2021)

Thongthee (2021) employed quasi-experimental research that aimed at exploring the effect of active learning approach on learners' achievement in English. The study was carried out at a secondary school in Thailand. It also examined students' level of satisfaction regarding the use of the jigsaw technique to teach them reading. Participants were 188 students divided into two groups. It also aimed at measuring students' attitudes towards the use of such a technique. The researchers collected data through classroom observation, pre- and posttest and questionnaire. The participants were 50 seventh-grade Indonesian students divided evenly into an experimental group and control group. The results showed that utilizing the jigsaw technique helped improve students' reading comprehension skill. Students also demonstrated a positive attitude towards integrating such a technique in their reading classes.

2.3.9 Current Study in Comparison to Previous Studies

There are some similarities as well as differences between the previously-mentioned studies on one hand, and the present study on the other. All of the studies mentioned above deal with either using different active learning techniques to enhance reading skills (Thongthee, 2021; Namaziandost, Gilakjani, & Hidayatullah, 2020; Qadan, 2018; Abrane, 2019; Tanapanyaworakul, 2020; Ragab, 2018) or increase classroom participation (Heswani, 2019; Mundelsee & Jurkowski, 2021). Most reviewed studies were conducted on young learners such as (Qadan, 2018; Ragab, 2018) or pre-intermediate learners (Namaziandost, Gilakjani, & Hidayatullah, 2020). Unlike the previous studies, this study deals with adult intermediate-level learners. Although Heswani (2019) dealt with adult intermediate learners, she did not deal with reading skills. Similar to Heswani's study, this study focuses on the level of participation using active learning techniques. However, as far as the researcher is concerned, this is the only study that concentrates on measuring the participation level in relation to EFL reading classes. To the researcher's best knowledge, it is the first in the Syrian context that implements active learning techniques to enhance learners' reading skills.

2.4 Summary of Chapter Two

This chapter highlighted the theoretical background of both active learning and reading skills. The concept of active learning and its theoretical background were discussed in detail. In addition, different types of active learning strategies were overviewed and the benefits of using these strategies were highlighted. Moreover, vital features of active learning such as learner's participation and engagement were discussed. The concept of reading as well as different skills and models were also highlighted. This chapter also presented previous studies which bear similar and different features to the current study.

Chapter Three

Methodology

This chapter discusses the methodology used in this research. It gives a full account of the design of the study, participants and data collection methods. It also presents the pilot study conducted to measure the validity and reliability of the data collection instruments. Finally, it gives a description of the data collection procedures including the treatment.

3.1. The Context of the Study

This study was carried out at the Higher Language Institute at Damascus University. The primary purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of implementing active learning techniques on improving learners' reading skill. To implement this study, a free course was announced and a sample of 40 students was gathered and examined. Twenty learners formed the experimental group, whereas the other 20 learners were part of the control group. The course was carried out during two weeks, from August 14th, 2022, until September 13th. Each group had a total of 8 sessions. Learners had to attend each session for two hours.

Participants were intermediate-level students aged between 19- 25. Moreover, all participants were university students majoring in different fields. Learners of the experimental group were instructed using active learning techniques, namely jigsaw, think-pair-share, and concept mapping, while learners of the control group were instructed through the use of mainly teacher-centered way.

3.2. The Design of the Study

The present study utilizes an experimental design which contains two groups: one experimental group and one control group. Both quantitative and qualitative data are gathered and analyzed. In order to determine if any relationship exists between the independent variable

(active learning techniques) and the dependent variable (reading skills), some statistical procedures had to be followed.

The researcher chose the topics to be discussed during the sessions based on their familiarity. To instruct learners of the experimental group, the researcher followed a three-phase model, namely pre-reading, while-reading and post-reading. Different active learning techniques were implemented at each stage such as jigsaw, think-pair-share, and concept maps. The teacher would implement techniques such as TPS in the pre-reading stage to activate learners' schemata, allow learners to share their experiences and raise their interest to read about the topic in hand. In the while-reading stage, the jigsaw and TPS were mainly used. As for the post-reading stage, concept mapping and TPS were done to check students' understanding and grant them the opportunity to analyze and evaluate what they had read.

On the other hand, learners of the control group were instructed in a traditional teacher-centered way. The teacher would start the session by introducing the topic and posing questions that allow learners to share their knowledge and experience regarding the topic. Next, the teacher would read aloud a short passage asking students to follow along in their textbooks and explain the meaning of the unfamiliar words or expressions. The following diagram illustrates the learning process for the experimental group.

Figure 3.1 *The Learning Process*

3.3 Data Collection Instruments

This research is a mixed-methods one. Both quantitative and qualitative data were collected. Quantitative data were gathered through the use of a pre- and posttest, classroom rubric and questionnaire. The qualitative data were obtained through two open-ended questions in the questionnaire. The pre- and posttest was utilized to evaluate whether carrying out certain active learning techniques has an effect on learners' reading skills before and after the treatment. The classroom rubric was mainly implemented to measure the level of learners' participation in both control and experimental groups during the learning process. As for the questionnaire, it was used to examine learners' attitudes towards active learning techniques.

3.4. Pilot Study

Prior to conducting the main experiment, a pilot study was carried out to make sure the data collection instruments were effective and appropriate. A sample of 20 EFL adult learners was examined. A placement test, which is used at the HLI, was administered to ensure that all learners had the required level. The materials to be taught were selected from the Outcomes course book, second edition, for the intermediate-level students. The selected reading passages

tackled different topics, including types of diets, costumes in different countries, jobs and shopping habits.

After selecting the materials, lesson plans for six reading passages were prepared. Students had to take the pre-test at the beginning of the course. The time allotted for the pre-test was an hour. During this two-week study, six reading texts were dealt with over eight sessions. The duration of each session varied from one hour and a half to two hours. At the end of the treatment, the collected data were statistically analyzed and modified accordingly.

3.4.1. Pre- and Posttest

To assess if using active learning techniques during EFL reading classes has any effect regarding improving learners' reading skill, a pre- and posttest was designed by the researcher, and it was based on six reading passages extracted from the Outcomes book for intermediate learners. The pre- and posttest consisted of 31 items which were reduced to 23 multiple-choice items due to high difficulty and easiness indices. The pre- and posttest was divided into two main parts. The first part aims at measuring learners' reading comprehension skill, whereas the second part attempts to assess learners' word recognition skill. The reading comprehension section contains a reading text and six questions related to its content. The vocabulary section consists of three cloze passages and choosing the appropriate meaning (See Appendix A). Prior to conducting the pilot study, the pre- and posttest was examined and approved by the researcher's supervisor.

3.4.1.1. Reading Test Reliability

Test reliability refers to the extent a test is likely to yield the same result when it is taken again. To measure the internal consistency of the pre- and posttest, Cronbach alpha was applied. Table 3.1 shows the reliability value of the reading pre-and posttest.

Table 3.1 Reading Test Reliability

Reliability	
Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
.776	23

Source: SPSS Outputs

Statistically speaking, Cronbach Alpha (also known as Alpha coefficient) ranges from (.00) to (1.00). The closer the value is to (1.00) the higher the reliability is. High values indicate that the items consistently measure the same construct. Positive and strong reliability coefficient should be equal to 0.7 or higher (Fraenkel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2012; Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2020). However, Nunnally and Bernstein (1994) suggest that a value equals or higher than 0.6 is acceptable and moderate. Table 3.1 shows that Cronbach Alpha reached 0.77 which is considered to be good and acceptable.

3.4.1.2. Difficulty Index of the Test

The difficulty index refers to the number of learners who have answered an item correctly (McCown, Driscoll, & Roop, 1995). It is usually expressed as a percentage that ranges from (-1) to (+1). High difficulty index value indicates an easier item. Educators such as Ebel and Frisbie (1991) suggest a value between 20-70%. However, Kehoe (1995) recommends a value between 30%- 80%, while Singh, Singh and Vinod (2003) suggest a value between 30%- 70%.

To calculate the difficulty and facility indices of the test submitted by 20 learners, the researcher used the following formula:

$$\text{Item difficulty} = \frac{\text{Number of correct answers}}{\text{Total number of students}} \times 100$$

Table 3.2 Difficulty & Easiness Indices of the Pre-test

Item No	PE	PD	Item No	PE	PD	Item No	PE	PD
1	75%	25%	9	45%	55%	17	70%	30%
2	75%	25%	10	50%	50%	18	50%	50%
3	45%	55%	11	60%	40%	19	50%	50%
4	35%	65%	12	55%	45%	20	80%	20%
5	70%	30%	13	40%	60%	21	55%	45%
6	50%	50%	14	20%	80%	22	45%	55%
7	60%	40%	15	75%	25%	23	50%	50%
8	35%	65%	16	50%	50%	-	-	-

PE= Percentage of easiness

PD= Percentage of difficulty

Source: SPSS Output

As the previous table shows, the average difficulty of the test items was 46%. All test items ranged from 20% to 70% except for one item that reached 80%. The other 22 items were moderate in their difficulty.

The table also shows that the average easiness of the test items was 53%, ranging from 35% to 80%. One Item exceeded the 70%, while the other 22 items were moderate in their easiness. The following figure illustrates the mean value of the difficulty and easiness indices.

Figure 3.2 Difficulty & Easiness Indices Mean Percentage

3.4.1.3 Discrimination Index of the Test

The discrimination index helps determine the effectiveness of an item. It refers to the extent a test item distinguishes learners who performed well on a test (high achievers) from those who performed poorly (low achievers) on the same test. It ranges from (-1) to (+1). High values indicate that the item has a high discrimination power. Items with negative discrimination value are undesirable and have to be eliminated. Some educators consider writing questions with perfect discrimination power is often not possible (Linn & Gronlund, 2000). An item with a value lower than 0.2 is considered to have a low but acceptable discrimination ability (Kehoe, 1995; Singh, Singh, & Vinod, 2003). Many educators, however, suggest that a value beyond 3 indicates excellent discrimination (Dreckmeyer & Fraser, 1991). To assess the discrimination index of the pre- and posttest, the following equation was applied:

$$\text{Discrimination Index (R)} = \frac{(H - L)}{27\% \text{ of total number of students}}$$

H = number of correct responses from 27% of high achievers

L = number of correct responses from 27% of low achievers

Table 3.3 Discrimination Index of the Pre-test Items

Item No	R Index						
1	0.30	7	0.36	13	0.58	19	0.48
2	0.18	8	0.48	14	0.43	20	0.30
3	0.56	9	0.36	15	0.28	21	0.48
4	0.46	10	0.38	16	0.25	22	0.50
5	0.16	11	0.18	17	0.38	23	0.26
6	0.48	12	0.58	18	0.46	-	-

Source: SPSS Output

As the aforementioned table shows, the discrimination index of test items ranges from 0.16 to 0.58, which is considered to be statistically good. The average discrimination value reaches 0.38. Three items have a less than 2 discrimination value, though. All other 20 items range from .30 to 0.58. The mean discrimination value reaches 0.39, which is regarded to be good.

Figure 3.3 Discrimination Indices of the Pre- & Posttest

3.4.2 Questionnaire

To measure learners’ attitude towards using active learning techniques in EFL reading classes, the researcher designed the questionnaire after reviewing and investigating related literature on active learning and reading skill, adapted mainly from studies conducted by Farzaneh and Nejadansari in (2014), Shih and Reynolds in (2015), and Gonazles and Torres in (2016). After having been approved by the researcher’s supervisor and two other faculty members, the questionnaire entitled “Learners’ Attitude towards Using Active Learning Strategies” was piloted on 20 adult EFL learners.

Since it is recommended that questionnaires should consist of both closed and open-ended items (Mackey & Gass, 2005), the questionnaire was divided into two parts and followed the five-choice Likert scale. On the one hand, the first part was subcategorized into three dimensions, namely content, participation and engagement. The second part, on the other hand, consisted of two questions that allow students to reflect and express their opinions regarding

the learning experience. As it is recommended that “whenever possible, questionnaires should be administered in the learners’ native language” (Mackey & Gass, 2005, p. 96), the questionnaire was distributed to the learners of the pilot group in Arabic.

3.4.2.1 Questionnaire Reliability

To make certain that the questionnaire can yield the same results upon re-administration, the reliability of the questionnaire was measured. Cronbach Alpha value was calculated for each dimension and for the total score of the questionnaire items. The following table shows Cronbach alpha value of the questionnaire.

Table 3.4 Reliability of the Questionnaire

Questionnaire Dimension	Cronbach Alpha
Content (sub-scale)	.708
Performance (sub-scale)	.832
Engagement (sub-scale)	.724
Total score	.892

The above table shows that the Cronbach alpha values for the questionnaire dimension and total score were high and positive, ranging between 708-892.

3.4.2.2 Questionnaire Validity

In order to check the construct validity of the questionnaire, Pearson’s correlation was calculated. As it is known in the statistical field, Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) is used to measure if there is a strong relationship between two variables. A linear relationship between variables represents a strong relationship between two variables. Pearson’s coefficient (r) ranges from (-1) to (+1). The closer the correlation coefficient value to (1) the stronger the

relationship between two variables. A negative value indicates a perfect negative linear relationship, whereas a (0) value implies no relationship at all (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015; Christensen, Johnson, & Turner, 2020). Therefore, the internal validity was measured by correlating the items of the questionnaire to their dimension and total score as the table below shows.

Table 3.5 The Correlation Coefficient of the Questionnaire

Dimension	Item	Correlation between an item and its dimension	Correlation between an item and total score	Correlation between dimension and total score
Content	1	831	746	947**
	2	607	627	
	3	802	488	
	4	707	589	
Performance	5	417	369	945**
	6	653	726	
	7	821	834	
	8	602	529	
	9	461	497	
	10	731	781	
	11	692	569	
	12	737	673	
	13	470	474	
	14	787	687	
En ga ge	15	555	507	805**

	16	792	849	
	17	575	669	
	18	547	568	
	19	469	517	
	20	398	506	
	21	415	624	
	22	370	521	
	23	456	413	

The previous table shows that the correlation value between each item and its dimension ranges from (370) to (831). Furthermore, the correlation value between each item and its total score ranges from (369) and (849), which indicate a positive correlation. Finally, the correlation value between each dimension and its total score was high and positive, ranging between (805) and (947).

3.4.2.2.2 Discriminant Validity

The questionnaire was piloted on 20 learners. To ensure that the questionnaire distinguishes learners who had a positive attitude regarding implementing active learning from those who had a negative attitude, the discrimination validity was calculated.

Scores were descending ordered and divided into two groups. The highest 27% of scores (6 learners' scores) formed the high group, whereas the lowest 27% of scores (6 learners' scores) formed the low group. The mean and the standard deviations of the two groups were calculated. Independent Samples t-Test was also applied to measure the significant difference between the two means on the total score of the questionnaire. The table below demonstrates the difference between the two groups:

Table 3.6 The Means, Standard Deviations, T Value and Significance

Dimension	Group	N	Mean	S.D	(t)	(sig)	Decision
Content	High	6	19.83	.40	16.97	.000	**Sig
	Low	6	15.83	.40			
Performance	High	6	48.16	1.47	10.50	.000	**Sig
	Low	6	39	1.54			
Engagement	High	6	43.83	1.39	11.57	.000	**Sig
	Low	6	35.33	1.21			
Total score	High	6	108.50	3.50	10.48	.000	**Sig
	Low	6	91.83	1.72			

Source: SPSS Output

As the above-table shows, there is a statistically significant difference between these two groups, in favor of the higher group. In other words, the questionnaire is valid and its items are of a high discriminative value.

3.5 Classroom Participation Rubric

One of the primary goals of active learning is to increase student’s engagement and participation in the classroom activities. Classroom participation can take various forms, including answering questions, making comments and joining discussions (Vandricks, 2000). It also involves taking part in role-playing, brainstorming and peer teaching activities (Zayapragassarazan & Kumar, 2012).

To assess participation in the classroom, various criteria were suggested. Dancer and Kamvounias (2005) developed a criterion to assess student’s participation, which was divided

into five key categories: preparation, contribution, group skills, communication skills and attendance. Bean and Peterson (1998) also proposed a holistic rubric for measuring class participation. They argued that although class participation is generally subjective, teachers can create holistic rubrics for assessing class participation, provided that they conceive what an ideal class will look like, link their visualization clearly to the expected learning outcomes and explain the rubric to learners.

For the purpose of measuring the classroom participation level in this study, the researcher adapted a specially-designed rubric based on Bean and Peterson's holistic rubric for scoring class participation. The "Class Participation Rubric" (Appendix D) was broken down into four categories, namely independence, participation, quality of participation and level of engagement. Each category had a scale ranging from (0) to (3) points. After being approved by the researcher's supervisor and a senior teacher at the HLI, this instrument was distributed to observer teachers to be used as an observation sheet for every session for both experimental and control groups.

3.6 Homogeneity Test

Homogeneity test is used to ensure that two samples derive from the same population. In other words, it refers to the degree a set of items measures a single construct. An Independent Samples t-Test was applied to compare the mean pre-test scores of the control group and experimental group to check whether there is difference between the selected samples for both groups prior to the treatment.

Table 3.7 Mean Scores of Control & Experimental Groups

Group	N	Mean	S.D	(t)	(df)	(sig)	Decision
Experimental Group	20	11.30	5.401	-0.175	38	0.862	Not significant
Control Group	20	11.60	5.413				

Source: SPSS Output

The following figure illustrates the mean score between the experimental group and control group

Figure 3.4 Mean Scores of Experimental & Control Groups

As it is noted from the previous table, both control and experimental groups are equal and homogenous. Hence, any difference that may exist later on between the two groups can be attributed to the treatment they have undergone.

3.7 Summary of Chapter Three

In summary, this chapter explained in detail the data collection tools and the procedures needed to conduct this research. In addition, it provided a brief account of the participants and the research context concentrating mainly on three instruments: the pre- and posttest, the questionnaire and the class participation rubric, and ensuring their validity, reliability, discrimination and difficulty indices. It also gives a detailed description of the pilot study procedure and the data validation process.

Chapter Four

Findings and Discussion

This chapter discusses the findings of this study. It begins with analyzing the quantitative data obtained by using the pre- and posttest and the classroom participation checklist. Then the qualitative and quantitative parts of the questionnaire were analyzed and reported. The results of this study were analyzed using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 26.

4.1. Introducing the Results of Question No. One

In an attempt to answer the first research question, a set of statistical measures was employed. Paired-Samples t-Tests were conducted to identify the level of difference among learners within the same group. On the other hand, Independent-Samples t-Tests were applied to estimate the level of difference between two groups.

4.1.1 Statistical Significance

Moreover, the aforementioned t-Tests enable the analyst to determine whether a difference is of statistical significance. These t-Tests indicate the significance of the impact of a treatment by its p-value. If the p-value is less than or equal to 0.05, the difference can be considered statistically significant. In contrast, if the p-value is greater than 0.05, the difference can be regarded as statistically insignificant.

4.1.2 Effect Size (Cohen's d)

Effect size is the measurement of the strength of a relationship or the magnitude of a difference between two groups' means. Since the p-value depends on the sample size and runs the risk that the intervention's significance value might be due to a small or large sample size, the effect size should be calculated and reported. Unlike the p-value, which determines if an

intervention has an effect, the effect size identifies the degree of difference or change. The effect size or Cohen’s *d* can be interpreted as the following table shows

Table 4.1 Cohen’s Conventions

Effect Size	<i>d</i>
Small	=0.20
Medium	=0.50
Large	=<0.80

Source: Cohen’s conventions. Adopted from “Using Effect Size- or Why the P-Value is not Enough” by Sullivan & Feinn. (2012). *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 4(3), 279-282

4.2 Results of Question No. One

4.2.1 First Question: What is the effect of using active learning techniques on improving EFL learners’ reading skills?

This question was measured by using a pre- and posttest. In order to answer the first question, three hypotheses were tested.

4.2.1.1 First Hypothesis: There are no statistically differences between the scores of the pretest and posttest of the experimental group participants

To find out whether there is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of participants of the experimental group before and after the treatment, the researcher calculated the mean score, the standard deviations and the standard errors of learners’ score of the pre- and the posttest. Table 4.2 shows learners’ scores of the experimental group on the pre- and posttest.

Table 4.2 Experimental Group's Pretest and Posttest Scores

Pre- and Posttest	Application	N	Mean	S.D	S.EM
	Pretest	20	11.30	5.401	1.208
	Posttest	20	21.05	2.164	.484

N: Number of Learners S.D: Standard Deviation S.EM: Standard Error Mean

Paired-Samples t-test was also applied to identify statistically the level of difference among learners of the experimental group in the pre- and posttest as shown in the table below.

Table 4.3 Paired-Samples t-Test Results of the Significant Difference among the Experimental Group Learners

Pre- and Posttest	Application	N	Mean	S.D	(t)	(df)	(sig)	Decision
	Pretest	20	11.30	5.401	-10.373	19	0,000	Sig**
	Posttest	20	21.05	2.164				

t: t-test value

DF: Degree of Freedom

Sig: Significance

The following chart illustrates the mean scores of learners in the experimental group

Figure 4.1 Mean Score of the Experimental Group

As it is shown in the previous table, the value of (t) reached (-10.373) at the significant value (0,000), which is smaller than the level of the significance value adopted in this research (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis is refuted and the alternative hypothesis is accepted; i.e. there is statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the pre- and posttest among learners. Thus, the implemented active learning techniques during the course had a positive impact on enhancing learners' level of reading.

4.2.1.1 Effect size for Paired Samples t-test of the Experimental Group

To identify the degree of change that the experimental group's learners underwent, the effect size was calculated by using the mean and standard deviation in the Paired-Samples t-Test as the following formula shows

$$d = \frac{\text{Mean}}{\text{S. D}}$$

Mean = 9.750

Standard deviation = 4.205

Effect size= 2.3

9.750 divided by 4.205 returns 2.3.

The *d* value represents the size of change of the experimental group. Depending on Cohen's conventions (see Table 4.3), the *d* value indicates a large size effect.

4.2.2 Second Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference between the mean score of the pre- and posttest of the control group participants.

Similarly, to identify any difference among the participants of the control group before and after the treatment, the mean scores, the standard deviations and the standard error of learners' pre- and posttest were calculated as the following table shows:

Table 4.4 Control Group's Pretest & Posttest Scores

Pre- and posttest	Application	N	Mean	S.D	S.EM
	Pre-test	20	11.95	5.185	1.159
	Post-test	20	12.75	5.599	1.252

Source: SPSS Output

As the above-mentioned table points out, the mean score of the control group in the pre-test was (11.95), whereas the mean score reached (12.75) in the post-test. Consequentially, the mean score of the control group improved by only (0.8), which is far less than the experimental group. The following figure illustrates the mean scores of the control group before and after the treatment:

Figure 4.2 Mean Score of the Control Group

Furthermore, the Paired-Samples t-test was used to determine if the level of difference between the control group participants in the pre- and posttest is statistically significant or not

Table 4.5 Paired-Samples t-Test of the Control Group

	Application	N	Mean	S.D	(t)	df	(sig)	Decision
Control group	Pre-test	20	11.95	5.185	-1.993	19	0.061	Not significant
	Post-test	20	12.75	5.599				

Source: SPSS Output

As the table clearly shows, the (t) value equals (-1.993), whilst the p-value is (0.061) which is greater than the level of significance adapted in this research (0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is no a statistically significant difference among the learners of the control group in the pre- and posttest.

4.2.2.1 Effect Size of Paired-Samples t-Test of the Control Group

The effect size was also calculated of the control group's pre- and posttest. It was computed by using the formula below depending on the data presented in the previous Paired-Samples t-Test:

$$d = \frac{\text{Mean}}{\text{S.D}}$$

Mean= 0.8

Standard deviation= 1.79

D= 0.45

The d value equals 0.45 which implies a small to medium effect size. However, this d value is smaller than the d value of the experimental group. Thus, using active learning techniques weighs in favor of the experimental group.

4.2.3 Third Hypothesis: There is no statistically significant difference between the mean score of the pre and posttest of the control group and the experimental group.

To evaluate the level of change between the experimental group and the control group's posttest, the mean score, standard deviations and the standard errors of the control group and the experimental group were calculated.

Table 4.6 Mean Scores of Pretest & Posttest of Experimental & Control Groups

	Group	N	Mean	S.D	S.EM
Posttest	Experimental	20	21.05	2.16	0.48
	Control	20	12.75	5.59	1.25

Source: SPSS Output

The previous table shows that the mean score of the experimental group posttest reached 21.05, while the mean score of the control group's posttest was estimated at 12.75. Therefore, the mean score of the experimental group was higher by 8.30 than that of the control group.

Figure 4.3 Mean Scores of Pretest & Posttest of Control & Experimental Groups

To measure the significance of the level of difference between the experimental and control groups' posttest, the Independent Samples t-test was applied.

Table 4.7 Results of Independent-Samples t-Test of Experimental & Control Group

	Application	N	Mean	S.D	(t)	df	(sig)	Decision
Posttest	Experimental	20	21.05	2.18	-6.183	38	0.000	Sig**
	Control	20	12.75	5.59				

Source: SPSS Output

The previous table shows that the (t) value equals (-6.183), while the p-value is (0.000) which is smaller than the level of significance adapted in this research. In consequence, the null

hypothesis is refuted, which means that there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of the post-test of the experimental and control groups.

This result confirms that learners of the experimental group outperformed learners of the control group. Consequentially, active learning techniques that were implemented during the reading sessions helped learners improve their performance and score higher than learners of the control group. These findings go in line with studies conducted by Namaziandost, Gilakjani and Hidayatullah in 2020, Ragab in 2018 and Qadan in 2019 in which they concluded that active learning techniques such as jigsaw, concept maps and TPS were effective in teaching EFL reading skills and yield better learning outcomes than some other traditional methods.

4.2.3.1 Effect Size for Independent-Samples t-Test of Experimental and Control Groups

In addition to the statistical significance implied by the p-value, the effect size of the difference between the experimental group and control group on the posttest was also calculated by using the formula below and the data presented in the Independent-Samples t-Test.

$$d = \frac{\text{mean1} - \text{mean2}}{s.d1 - s.d2} / 2$$

Using the above-mentioned formula, the effect size is estimated at 1.95, which entails a large effect size. Thus, it can be concluded that the size of difference between the control group and experimental group on the posttest is large.

4.3 Results of Question No. Two

4.3.1 Second Question: To what extent will learners' participation level be improved?

To answer this question, the following hypothesis was tested:

There is no significant difference between the level of participation of the control group and the experimental group

To evaluate the level of classroom participation, the researcher adapted a pre-designed checklist from Bean and Peterson (1998). This checklist was divided into four categories, namely independence, participation, quality of participation and level of engagement. Each category has a scale ranging from 0 to 3 for a total of 12 points. To fill in the checklist, an observer attended each class for both control group and experimental group.

To find out if there is any statistically difference between the level of participation between the control and experimental groups, the mean and standard deviations of the scores of the two groups were calculated for each category. The table below demonstrates the scores of each group for each category.

Table 4.8 Participation Level Scores of Experimental & Control Groups

Category	Group	N	Mean	S.D
Independence	Experimental group	6	2.5	5.4
	Control group	6	0.6	5.1
Participation	Experimental group	6	3	0
	Control group	6	0.8	0.4
Quality of Participation	Experimental group	6	3	0
	Control group	6	0.8	0.4
Level of Engagement	Experimental group	6	3	0
	Control group	6	0.8	0.4

N: number of lessons

Source: SPSS Output

As the aforementioned table shows, the mean scores of the participation level of the experimental group were higher than those of the control group. On the one hand, the mean score of the engagement, participation and quality of participation reached 3, meanwhile the mean score of the level of independence was a little lower and reached 3. On the other hand, the mean score of the control group for the independence category was 0.6, while the mean score for the participation, quality of participation and level of engagement categories reached 0.8. This means that active learning techniques that were used during the experimental group's instruction helped increase the level of participation in the classroom and were more effective than the traditional method. Learners were able to offer ideas, ask questions and make comments. They also had the chance to discuss with their peers their views and share their experiences. In addition, learners displayed consistent participation and engagement in the assigned tasks and took the initiative to complete them. These findings confirm the previous studies that state that active learning helps increase learners' in-class participation level and engagement (Heswani, 2019, Freeman et al., 2014), motivate learners to participate with confidence (Mundelsee & Jurkowski, 2021) and provide learners with opportunities to improve their communication skills (Namaziandost, Gilakjani & Hidayatullah., 2020).

The following diagram shows the mean scores of the participation level for both the experimental and control groups.

Figure 4.4 Learners' Participation Scores for Experimental & Control Groups

4.3.2 Mann-Whitney U-Test

Mann-Whitney u-test is used to measure statistically the difference between two measures. The smaller the p-value is, the less the chance is that this difference is random or occurred by accident. Hence, if the probability level (*p value*) is equal or smaller than 0.05, the null hypothesis can be rejected. To identify if there is any significant difference in the level of participation between the control and experimental groups, the Mann-Whitney U-test was run.

Table 4.9 Mann-Whitney U-test Results of both Experimental & Control Groups'

Participation Level

Category	Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	(U)	(Z)	sig	Decision
Independence	Experimental group	6	9.50	57	0.000	-3	0.002	Significant
	Control group	6	3.50	21				

Participation	Experimental group	6	9.33	56	1.000	-2	0.004	Significant
	Control group	6	3.67	22				
Quality of Participation	Experimental group	6	9.42	56	0.500	-2	0.003	Significant
	Control group	6	3.58	21				
Level of Engagement	Experimental group	6	9.50	57	0.000	-3	0.002	Significant
	Control group	6	3.50	21				

Source: SPSS Output

As the previous table noted, the probability value (p-value) for the independence, participation, quality of participation and level of engagement ranges from (0,002) to (0,004), which is smaller than (0,05). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means there is statistically significant difference in the level of participation between the experimental group and control group.

4.4. Results of Question No. Three

4.4.1 Third Question: What is the attitude of learners towards using active learning techniques?

To answer the third and final question of this research, a 24-item questionnaire was used to measure learners' attitude towards using active learning techniques in teaching EFL reading skills. The questionnaire consists of three dimensions, namely content, performance and engagement followed by two open-ended questions.

4.4.1.1 Results of Closed-Ended Questions

As mentioned previously, this part of questionnaire contains questions related to the content, engagement and participation dimensions.

4.4.1.2 Content

This dimension contains 4 questions about learners' attitude towards learning the content through active learning strategies. The frequency and percentage of learners' responses are calculated and shown in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10 Frequency & Percentage of Content Theme

No	Statement	Responses				
		Freq.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutra l	Disagree
1.	Active learning helps me understand the content better.	8 40%	12 60%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
2.	Active learning is an interesting way of learning the material.	10 50%	10 50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
3.	Learning the material becomes less difficult during active learning activities.	10 50%	9 45%	0 0%	1 5%	0 0%
4.	Working on a well-organized task makes learning more effective.	8 40%	12 60%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%

Source: SPSS Output

The previously-mentioned table shows that from 90% to 95% of learners think that studying the material through active learning techniques was interesting and more effective.

They also agreed that such techniques made the content easier to understand. The following diagram summaries the percentages of the learners’ responses of the content dimension.

Figure 4.5 Frequency & Percentage of Content Theme

4.4.1.3 Performance

This dimension consists of 9 questions about how using active techniques helps students improve their performance. The table below shows the frequencies and percentages of learners’ responses.

Table 4.11 Frequency & Percentage of Performance Theme

No	Statement	Responses				
		Freq	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree
5.	I prefer to study the content on my own.	0	0	6	11	3
		0%	0%	30%	55%	15%

6.	I am more motivated to learn about the content through active learning activities.	8 40%	11 55%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%
7.	Active learning discourages me to learn about the topic.	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	14 70%	6 30%
8.	Interacting with my classmates help me improve my performance.	14 70%	5 25%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%
9.	Active learning helps me retain information for a longer time.	13 65%	6 30%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%
10.	I can share my knowledge with my classmates.	10 50%	10 50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
11.	I achieve more when I work with my classmates.	8 40%	9 45%	3 15%	0 0%	0 0%
12.	Active learning encourages me to improve my reading abilities.	9 45%	7 35%	3 15%	1 5%	0 0%
13.	Having to share my knowledge with other students makes me feel uncomfortable.	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	10 50%	10 50%
14.	Active learning helps me take control of my own learning.	3 15%	14 70%	3 15%	0 0%	0 0%

Source: SPSS Output

As the previous table shows, 95% of learners think that active learning techniques help them enhance their performance and recall information better, which are main advantages of

active learning identified by Freeman et al (2014) and Prince in (2004). Moreover, 95% of learners were more motivated to learn the content through these techniques and 70% of them rejected to study the content on their own. 75% of learners agree that these techniques encouraged them to perfect their reading skills. Learners' responses also show that active learning techniques granted them the opportunity to have a central role in the learning process by taking responsibility for their own learning, which is an important goal of any active learning technique. The following chart illustrates the percentage of learners' responses.

Figure 4.6 Frequency & Percentage of the Performance Theme

4.4.1.4 Engagement

This dimension has 10 questions about learners' participation in the classroom. The frequencies and percentages of learners' responses were calculated as the table below shows.

Table 4.12 Frequency & Percentage of Engagement Theme

No	Statement	Responses					
		Freq.	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
15.	I enjoy studying the content more with other students.	6 30%	13 65%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%	
16.	I willingly participate in active learning activities.	6 30%	14 70%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	
17.	I prefer that my teacher uses more interactive activities.	10 50%	10 50%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	
18.	I can participate confidently in the lessons.	5 25%	11 55%	4 20%	0 0%	0 0%	
19.	I feel bored and concerned during the activities.	0 0%	0 0%	1 5%	15 75%	4 20%	
20.	Active learning enhances the level of participation in class.	7 35%	13 65%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	
21.	Active learning gives equal opportunities to participate in the lessons.	4 20%	13 65%	3 15%	0 0%	0 0%	
22.	I learn to work with students who are different from me. (level, background, opinion)	10 50%	9 45%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%	
23.	I am able to communicate better with my classmates.	5 25%	14 70%	1 5%	0 0%	0 0%	

Source: SPSS Output

The majority of learners enjoyed having the reading classes delivered through the use of active learning techniques and were able to communicate and get to know their classmates better. Learners also showed their interest in using more interactive techniques. Furthermore, 85% of learners were able to participate with confidence during the sessions. All in all, the results of the questionnaire are in agreement with the findings of other studies. The results assert that active learning techniques lead to better learners' attitudes (Freeman et al., 2014), and enhance their confidence and motivation to learn (Namaziandost, Gilakjani & Hidayatullah, 2020, Qadan, 2018). They also gave learners the opportunity to learn from each other (Gonzales & Torres, 2016). The following figure the frequency and percentage of learners' responses of the engagement theme.

Figure 4.7 Frequency & Percentage of the Engagement Theme

4.5 Results of Open-ended Questions

The qualitative part of this questionnaire involves two questions that allow learners to reflect on their experience. The first question is as follows:

4.5.1 What activity did you like most? Why?

The frequency and percentage of learners' responses were calculated as shown in Table 4.13.

Table 4.13 *The Frequency & Percentage of Learners' Responses*

Activities	Frequency	Percentage
Jigsaw	9	50%
TPS	4	25%
Concept Mapping	4	25%

Source: SPSS Output

The following pie chart illustrates the percentage of learners' responses.

Figure 4.8 *The Most-liked Active Learning Technique by Learners*

As the previous table shows, 50% of learners preferred the jigsaw activity since it allowed students to share their thoughts with each other, helped them understand the materials better and assisted them to participate with confidence. 25% of learners preferred TPS because it allowed learners to exchange ideas and have a central role in the learning process. Another

25% of learners preferred using concept mapping as it is a good way of organizing and retaining information. Table 4.14, Table 4.15 and Table 4.16 show the percentage of learners' responses in detail.

Table 4.14 Learners' Preference of Jigsaw

Jigsaw	Frequency	Percentage
Exchange ideas and thoughts with other students	5	25%
Understand the topic better	3	15%
Participating with confidence in the discussions.	2	10%

Table 4.15 Learners' Preference of TPS

TPS	Frequency	Percentage
Having a central role in the learning process	3	15%
Sharing experiences and thoughts	2	10%

Table 4.16 Learners' Preference of Concept Mapping

Concept Mapping	Frequency	Percentage
Organizing my thoughts	2	12.5%
Remembering information better	2	12.5%

4.5.2 Do you have any suggestion to improve the learning process?

The second open-ended question is concerned with learners' suggestions to make the active learning experience better. Learners' responses were calculated as shown in the table below.

Table 4.17 Learners' Suggestions for Improving the Learning Experience

Suggestion	Frequency	Percentage
No suggestion	12	60%
Reading aloud exercise	2	10%
Using more activities	3	15%
Using games	3	15%

Source: SPSS Output

Figure 4.9 Learners' Suggestions for Improving the Learning Experience

Figure 4.9 illustrates that 15% of learners recommend using games which helps create a competitive atmosphere, while 15% of learners suggest using more activities. 10% of learners suggested having a read-aloud activity. However, the majority of learners had no suggestions for improving the active learning experience.

4.6 Summary of Chapter Four

This chapter addressed in detail the findings of the study in question. It began with introducing the followed statistical procedures. After stating the hypotheses and research questions, the results were analyzed and explained in detail. Results of the first question showed that utilizing active learning strategies does improve learners' performance. As for the second question, the results affirm that active learning increases the level of participation in the classroom. Also, learners showed a positive attitude regarding active learning and were motivated to learn. Active learning fostered learners' confidence as well.

Chapter Five

Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter provides conclusions to this study and it is divided into four sections. The first section gives a brief summary concerning the research objectives and procedures. The second section summarizes the main findings of the present research. The third section provides numerous recommendations for future research and EFL teachers. Finally, the fourth section of this chapter highlights the limitations of the current study.

5.1 Summary of the Research

This research was conducted to find out whether using active learning techniques can help EFL learners improve their reading skill and enhance the level of classroom participation. It also aimed at investigating learners' attitude towards using such strategies in EFL reading classes. To achieve this purpose, a free course was held at the HLI and a sample of 40 intermediate-level adult learners was examined. Learners were divided equally into two groups: an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group was instructed through implementing active learning techniques such as jigsaw, TPS, and concept mapping, whereas the control group was instructed using the teacher-centered approach. Both groups were instructed for two weeks and for two hours for each class.

To collect data, the researcher used three main instruments: a pre- and posttest, a classroom participation rubric and questionnaire. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected and analyzed. The researcher analyzed the collected data by using SPSS software 22 version. T-tests as well as descriptive statistics were conducted and reported.

5.2 Summary of the Results

The results of this research can be summarized as the following:

1. There is statistically a significant difference between the mean score of learners of the experimental group and control group. In other words, learners of the experimental group outperformed those of the control group. Therefore, active learning is considered to be a better method for teaching EFL reading than the traditional teacher-centered approach.
2. Active learning techniques enhanced classroom participation level. Such techniques improved learners' engagement, independence and their quality of participation. Meanwhile, the teacher-centered approach was far less effective in achieving this aim.
3. Learners had a positive attitude towards using active learning techniques in EFL reading classes. Learners were more motivated and interested to study the assigned materials through group work and discussion. Moreover, learners were able to understand and retain the materials presented through active learning better.

5.3 Recommendations

This section highlights some recommendations based on the analysis of the findings of this research for both future research and EFL teachers.

5.3.1 Recommendations for Further Research

Since the current study was limited to investigating the effect of using certain active learning techniques to foster EFL reading, it is recommended that other researchers take the following suggestions into consideration:

1. Apply active learning techniques on learners with other levels such as upper-intermediate and advanced levels.
2. Conduct research on a bigger sample size and for a longer period of time.
3. Consider applying active learning techniques to develop other language skills such as listening and speaking.

4. Apply other active learning techniques such as debates and strip-story.
5. Consider studying the effect that active learning techniques have on learner's autonomy.
6. Consider examining the effect of using some reading strategies such as visualization and metacognitive skills on enhancing learners' comprehension.
7. Consider investigating the relationship between visualization and creating concept maps in teaching reading and listening skills.

5.3.2 Recommendations for Teachers

The findings of this research also entail some important points for EFL teachers. Six recommendations are stated below:

1. Apply the active learning approach to create interactive learning environment.
2. Assume the role of the teacher as a facilitator and guide rather than being "sage on the stage"
3. Apply active learning techniques to raise learners' interest and keep them engaged.
4. Be trained on employing the jigsaw and think-pair-share and other active learning techniques in reading classes.
5. Students should also be trained on how to participate and work with their classmates.
6. Participate in seminars and workshops about active learning and its various methods and techniques.
7. Train students to employ reading strategies to enhance their comprehension.

5.4 Limitations of the Current Research

This study has some limitations that should be taken into consideration. These limitations involve the following:

1. Due to time limit, this research was carried out during two weeks only.
2. This study was conducted on intermediate-level learners.
3. It was applied on a sample of 40 learners only.
4. Jigsaw, TPS and concept mapping were mainly used in this research.
5. The main focus was on reading comprehension and vocabulary skills.

In conclusion, active learning is an effective approach for EFL reading instruction. It results in increasing the level of learners' participation and engagement. Also, implementing active learning techniques fosters learners' motivation and performance. Finally, active learning techniques play a vital role in enhancing EFL learners' reading ability.

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Appendix A

Pre- and Posttest

Damascus University

Faculty of Arts and Humanities

MA in Applied Linguistics

I. Reading Comprehension Section:

A. Read the following text. Then choose the best answer.

It all starts at the doors to the store. This is the usual position for trolleys and baskets. Flowers, fruit and vegetables are also often at the entrance. Flowers create a welcoming atmosphere, and buying fruit & vegetables makes you feel healthy. After you have chosen your apples, carrots and salad, you won't feel so guilty about picking up chocolate, crisps and beer later.

It's all about the senses. The smell of freshly-baked bread from a supermarket bakery makes you feel hungry, and so makes you buy more. Over two weeks, one supermarket played French or German music. When the French music was played, they sold more French food and when they played German music, sales of German food went up.

The more you see, the more you want to shop. Essentials such as milk, bottled water or bread are often positioned at the back of the store, making you walk past hundreds of other products. Supermarkets are designed to make you stop as often as possible because of narrow **aisles**, special offers, or free samples.

Every product has its place. New or popular items are often found at the end of aisles, on displays known as "end caps". Manufacturers pay extra for these prominent positions. Shelving is also important. The most expensive items are at adult eye level, with the brands above and below often at lower prices. Grabbing the first pack is easy, but might be hard on your pocket. And you don't escape when you **queue up** at the checkout. This is where you get bored waiting, and add magazines, sweets and chocolates to your trolley.

1. Companies have to pay more money if they want their products to ...

A. get sold rapidly.

- B. be clearly displayed.
- C. be well-advertised.
- D. get recommended to other people.

2. Expensive brands are usually placed ...

- A. at the end of the aisles.
- B. on middle shelves.
- C. at the front of the store.
- D. on top shelves.

3. Free samples & special offers ...

- A. make your shopping trip as long as possible.
- B. make you finish your shopping as soon as possible.
- C. help you choose a better product.
- D. help supermarkets get rid of bad products.

4. Waiting for a long time to pay for your stuff makes you ...

- A. give up shopping quickly.
- B. add extra items on your shopping list.
- C. cross some items off your shopping list.
- D. buy expensive items.

5. One of the following is NOT true about supermarkets ...

- A. Supermarkets promote expensive products.
- B. Supermarkets get you to spend a lot of money.
- C. Supermarkets make sure shoppers get the best bargains.
- D. Supermarkets waste your money and time.

6. The best title of the article is ...

- A. Supermarkets improve local areas

- B. Supermarkets make life easier
- C. Supermarkets get you to spend more
- D. Supermarkets' design have changed drastically

B. Choose the correct meaning of the following:

7. "Queue up"

- A. wait in a line B. quit
- C. leave in a hurry D. give up

8. "Aisle"

- A. area B. roof
- C. circle D. passage

II. Vocabulary Section:

A. Complete the following paragraphs with the correct word.

A. This is someone who often goes all day without eating anything at all. They will almost certainly (9) breakfast and if you invite them for lunch, they will usually make an excuse about being too busy. By dinner time, they are (10) hungry, and so consume a huge number of calories in one go. Preferring to eat by themselves, they tend to be fast eaters who don't (11) in shared meals with family or friends.

- 9. A. escape B. skip
- C. delay D. leave
- 10. A. fattening B. starving
- C. greasy D. filling
- 11. A. exchange B. take part
- C. involve D. join

B. A good curriculum vitae, with information about you and your qualifications and experience will (12) your chances of getting an interview for a job, but a poor CV could (13) everything before you even start. On average, a recruiter will spend just 15 or 20 seconds reviewing a CV, so it's important to get it right.

- 12. A. decrease B. boost
- C. blow D. miss
- 13. A. ruin B. solve

C. improve

D. adopt

B. Work out the meaning of the following sentences.

14. “Levels of stress among workers are very high. They often work in cramped conditions and have little opportunity to laugh or joke with their co-workers.” This means

- A. The relationship among workers is great.
- B. Workers are kept so busy.
- C. Workers are left satisfied.
- D. Workers are happy with their work.

15. “The fast-food fans tend to like strong flavors, and find fresh fruit and vegetables rather bland.” This means

- A. Fruit & vegetables are tasteless.
- B. Fruit & vegetables are delicious and healthy.
- C. Fruit & vegetables are useless
- D. Fruit & vegetables are the best flavors.

16. “I don’t have a problem with interviews. The hard part is getting your foot in the door.” This means

- A. It’s difficult to get started at a job.
- B. It’s important to make a good first impression.
- C. It’s important to get a job interview.
- D. It’s difficult to build good relationship with your co-workers.

17. “Online learning allows me to work at my own pace because of my job.” This means

- A. I miss many classes because of my work.
- B. I can exchange the materials at a fixed time.
- C. I can study as slowly or quickly as I like.
- D. I can study wherever I want.

C. Choose the best word that completes the meaning of the following sentences.

18. When you go out with people of your own age all the men offer to pay for everything. Back at home we just the bill between everyone.

- A. collect B. afford
- C. split D. borrow

19. preserve dead bodies in preparation for funerals.

- A. Volunteers B. Embalmers
- C. Employees D. Candidates

20. Workers in a recycling plant have to find recyclable items from a big pile of rubbish and for the minimum

- A. obsession B. competition
- C. abuse D. wage

21. I hadn't planned to go back to studying, but then I a TV program on the history of art and I found the whole thing fascinating.

- A. came across B. got by
- C. looked around D. ran by

22. The general grazer doesn't often sit down to a proper meal, preferring to just grab smaller to eat throughout the day.

- A. bites B. fries C. bags D. peas

23. I'll never get used to "stinky tofu". I tried it once. The sauce was actually OK, but that smell is just so

- A. pleasant B. off-putting
- C. fascinating D. outstanding

The End

Best of Luck

Appendix B

Learners' Attitude Towards Active Learning (English)

Damascus University

Faculty of Arts & Humanities

MA in Applied Linguistics

Learners' Attitude Towards Active Learning

This questionnaire has been designed to investigate learners' attitude towards using active learning strategies to improve their reading skills.

Directions: Read each statement carefully and check the response that expresses your opinion.

No.	Statement	Responses				
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1.	Active learning helps me understand the content better.	<input type="radio"/>				
2.	I prefer to study the content on my own.	<input type="radio"/>				
3.	Active learning is an interesting way of learning the material.	<input type="radio"/>				
4.	Learning the material becomes less difficult during active learning activities.	<input type="radio"/>				

5.	Working on a well-organized task makes learning more effective.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Part B- Performance		Responses				
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
6.	I am more motivated to learn about the content through active learning activities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7.	Active learning discourages me to learn about the topic.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8.	Interacting with my classmates help me improve my performance.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9.	Active learning helps me retain information for a longer time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10.	I can share my knowledge with my classmates.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11.	I achieve more when I work with my classmates.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
12.	Active learning encourages me to improve my reading abilities.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13.	Having to share my knowledge with other students makes me feel uncomfortable.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14.	Active learning helps me take control of my own learning.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Part C- Engagement		Responses				
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree

15.	I enjoy studying the content more with other students.	<input type="radio"/>				
16.	I willingly participate in active learning activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
17.	I prefer that my teacher uses more interactive activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
18.	I can participate confidently in the lessons.	<input type="radio"/>				
19.	I feel bored and concerned during the activities.	<input type="radio"/>				
20.	Active learning enhances the level of participation in class.	<input type="radio"/>				
21.	Active learning gives equal opportunities to participate in the lessons.	<input type="radio"/>				
22.	I learn to work with students who are different from me. (level, background, opinion)	<input type="radio"/>				
23.	I am able to communicate better with my classmates.	<input type="radio"/>				

Open-ended questions	
24.	What activity do you like the most? Why?
25.	What suggestions do you have to improve this learning experience?

Thank you!

Appendix C

Learners' Attitude Towards Active Learning (Arabic)

جامعة دمشق

كلية الآداب والعلوم الإنسانية

درجة الماجستير في اللغويات التطبيقية

استبيان آراء المتعلمين حول أنشطة التعلم النشط

تم تصميم هذا الاستبيان لقياس آراء المتعلمين حول استخدام استراتيجيات التعلم النشط لتحسين مهارات القراءة لدى متعلمي اللغة الإنجليزية لغة أجنبية.

التوجيهات: اقرأ العبارات بدقة ثم ضع إشارة عند الإجابة التي تعبر عن رأيك.

الإجابة					العبارة	الرقم
أوافق بشدة	أوافق	حيادي	لا أوافق	لا أوافق مطلقاً	المحتوى:	
<input type="radio"/>	التعلم النشط طريقة ممتعة لتعلم المحتوى.	1.				
<input type="radio"/>	العمل على نشاط منظم يجعل التعلم أكثر فعالية.	2.				
<input type="radio"/>	يساعدني التعلم النشط على فهم المحتوى بشكل أفضل.	3.				
<input type="radio"/>	يصبح تعلم المحتوى أقل صعوبة باستخدام أنشطة التعلم النشط.	4.				
<input type="radio"/>	أفضل دراسة المحتوى بمفردي.	5.				
الإجابة					الأداء:	
أوافق بشدة	أوافق	حيادي	لا أوافق	لا أوافق مطلقاً		
<input type="radio"/>	أشعر بالحماس لتعلم المحتوى من خلال أنشطة التعليم النشط.	6.				
<input type="radio"/>	يعيق التعلم النشط عملية تعلم المحتوى.	7.				

0	0	0	0	0	8. يساعدني التفاعل مع أصدقائي على تحسين أدائي.
0	0	0	0	0	9. يساعدني التعلم النشط على تذكر المعلومات لفترة أطول.
0	0	0	0	0	10. أستطيع مشاركة معرفتي مع زملائي بالصف.
0	0	0	0	0	11. أنجز الكثير عندما أعمل مع زملائي بالصف.
0	0	0	0	0	12. يشجعني التعليم النشط على تحسين قدرات القراءة لدي.
0	0	0	0	0	13. أشعر بعدم الراحة عند مشاركة معرفتي مع الطلاب الآخرين.
0	0	0	0	0	14. يساعدني التعلم النشط على الاعتماد على نفسي باكتساب المعلومة.
الإجابة					المشاركة:
أوافق بشدة	أوافق	محايد	لا أوافق	لا أوافق مطلقاً	
0	0	0	0	0	15. استمتع أكثر بدراسة المحتوى مع الطلاب الآخرين.
0	0	0	0	0	16. أشرك برغبة بأنشطة التعليم النشط.
0	0	0	0	0	17. أفضل أن يستخدم المعلم المزيد من الأنشطة التفاعلية.
0	0	0	0	0	18. أشرك بثقة ونشاط بأنشطة التعليم خلال الأنشطة.
0	0	0	0	0	19. أشعر بالضجر والقلق خلال الأنشطة.
0	0	0	0	0	20. يحسن التعليم النشط مستوى المشاركة بالصف.
0	0	0	0	0	21. يتيح لي التعلم النشط الفرصة للعمل مع طلاب ذو مقدره مختلفه عني.
0	0	0	0	0	22. يتيح التعلم النشط فرص متساوية للمشاركة بالدروس.
0	0	0	0	0	23. أستطيع أن اتواصل بشكل أفضل مع زملائي بالصف.

الأسئلة المفتوحة

<p>24. ما هو النشاط الذي أعجبك أكثر؟ لماذا؟</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	
<p>25. هل لديك أي اقتراحات لتحسين التجربة التعليمية؟</p> <p>.....</p> <p>.....</p>	

شكرا لك!

Appendix D

Classroom Participation Rubric

Observer:

Lesson title

Date:

Class Participation Rubric

Criteria	Scale			
	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1. Independence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Self-directed and highly motivated. ▪ Take ownership of their learning as most class time is allocated to interact and reflect on their learning. ▪ Have the opportunity to construct viable arguments. 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Participation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Contribute without prompting. ▪ Offer ideas and/or asks questions. ▪ Participate actively in classroom activities. 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Quality of Participation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Proactively contribute to completing the classroom activities. ▪ Make thoughtful comments. ▪ Demonstrate consistent ongoing involvement. 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Level of Engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Work with class, group, and peers to achieve meaningful tasks. ▪ Respond thoughtfully to other students' comments, building on the ideas and contributions of others. ▪ Engage in their work and conversations with classmates. 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Grading: Always = 3	Sometimes = 2	Rarely = 1	Never = 0
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Appendix E

Concept Mapping Sample

A Concept map for a reading text entitled “Tips for Writing a Better CV?”

ملخص

أجريت هذه الدراسة على 40 متعلم للغة الإنكليزية لغة أجنبية في المعهد العالي للغات في جامعة دمشق في سوريا وتم توزيع المتعلمين الأربعين بشكل متساوٍ إلى مجموعتين: مجموعة تجريبية (طبقت عليها استراتيجيات التعلم النشط) ومجموعة معيارية (درّست من خلال استخدام طرق تقليدية). إن الهدف الأساسي لهذه الدراسة هو البحث في تأثير استخدام تقنيات التعلم النشط على مهارات القراءة لدى متعلمي اللغة الإنكليزية لغة أجنبية. كما تهدف الدراسة إلى معرفة ما إذا كان تطبيق تقنيات التعلم النشط يمكن أن يحسن مستوى المشاركة في الصف. وتهدف الدراسة الحالية أيضاً إلى قياس آراء المتعلمين حول تقنيات التعلم النشط المستخدمة في هذه الدراسة في تعلم مهارات القراءة. وقد تم جمع البيانات الكمية والنوعية من خلال استخدام ثلاث أدوات رئيسية: استبيان واختبار قبل المعالجة واختبار بعد المعالجة ومقياس المشاركة داخل الصف. أشارت نتائج الدراسة إلى أن لاستخدام التعلم النشط تأثيراً إيجابياً على أداء ومشاركة المتعلمين. كما أظهر المتعلمون آراءً إيجابية حول استخدام تلك التقنيات في تعليم مهارات القراءة، حيث أكد الطلاب أن تلك التقنيات انعكست إيجاباً على أدائهم ومشاركتهم وعززت الثقة لديهم والحافز للتعلم. وأوصت الدراسة بـجوب إدخال تقنيات التعلم النشط لتدريس مهارات القراءة في صفوف تعليم اللغة الإنكليزية لغة أجنبية.

الجمهورية العربية السورية

جامعة دمشق

كلية الآداب والعلوم الإنسانية

قسم اللغة الإنكليزية

توظيف استراتيجيات التعلم النشط لتحسين مهارات القراءة لدى متعلمي اللغة الإنكليزية

لغة أجنبية

رسالة أعدت في كلية الآداب والعلوم الإنسانية في جامعة دمشق، وهي جزء من متطلبات نيل درجة الماجستير في

اللغويات التطبيقية

تقديم الباحثة

بانه مصري

بإشراف

الدكتورة ميسون مزاحم

دمشق 2022-2023